

Russia is winning the Disinformation War with Ukraine

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ABSTRACT

Russian Foreign Malign Influence (FMI) campaigns include propaganda, weaponized information, and disinformation. Russian disinformation is content developed explicitly by Russian intelligence services and/or their proxies to intensify the effect of FMI and Weaponized Information on American society, as well as all other Western-style democratic societies. One method Russia uses to spread disinformation is by using fake news sites. Russian fake news sites typically masquerade online as US-based news sites and propel false narratives to their audience. The content on Russian faux news sites is often used as a method to manipulate the American public by creating discord. However, discord is not the only upside for Russian leaders. Russia's goal is to influence American citizens, U.S. domestic policy, and U.S. foreign policy, specifically as it relates to the war in Ukraine. For this strategy to be effective, the disinformation aimed at the American public must appear to be authentic. Also, elected officials must amplify and repeat the information to reinforce confirmation bias in the U.S. citizenry who may have voted for those same political leaders. Towards this endeavor, disinformation flows consistently from Russian state-controlled media such as Russia Today News (RT News) and Sputnik News that is intended to capture the attention of U.S. based media outlets. Furthermore, Russia funds large swaths of fake and legitimate news media outlets such as Tennessee-based Tenet Media, which, according to U.S. prosecutors, is a front for a Russian influence operation. Regrettably, Tenet Media is not a rarity. There are a significant number of fake news outlets in the U.S. that are funded, heavily influenced by, and/or outright controlled by Russian security services. As a result, fraudulent sites are very successful at masquerading as legitimate sites. These faux sites influence social media personalities and their audiences to believe wildly inaccurate disinformation, especially regarding Russia's war with Ukraine. Most alarming is the fact that far too many American citizens are not only susceptible to this manipulative strategy but are also unwitting co-conspirators.

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On February 24, 2022, Russia invaded Ukraine, and media outlets worldwide covered the Russian invasion, providing 24/7 coverage. On February 19, 2025, President Donald Trump blamed Ukraine's leaders for Russia's invasion. "You should have never started it," Mr. Trump said, referring to Ukraine's leaders. "You could have made a deal."¹ This remark by Trump was preceded by and followed up with a blitzkrieg of Russian propaganda and disinformation. Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelenskyy responded Wednesday to President Trump's accusation overnight that Ukraine started its war with Russia, saying that Trump is trapped in a "Russian disinformation bubble."² If Zelenskyy is correct and Trump does live in a disinformation bubble, he's not there alone. A YouGov poll published Wednesday, February 19th, shows that while most Americans believe that Russia started the war with the Ukraine at 61 percent, 6 percent believe it was Ukraine who began the conflict. Fifteen percent of Americans think both countries shared equal blame, and 18 percent said, "not sure."³

Figure 1.0: YouGov Survey on "Who do you think started the war between Russian and Ukraine?"⁴

The numbers in figure 1.0 may seem insignificant, considering only 6 percent of adults surveyed agree with President Trump about who started the war. However, the 18 percent of Americans who are "not sure" should be jarring to those who believe that foreign malign influence doesn't have a significant impact. This survey reveals three levels of effectiveness of Russian malign influence campaigns. Eighteen percent represent uncertainty, level three. The 15 percent who believe both nations started the war represent bewilderment, level two. Lastly, the percent who blame Russia represents the holistically inaccurate, level one. Arguably, the 18 percent in level three could graduate to level 2, and maybe even level one if saturated with enough disinformation. However, even if these numbers remain fixed, this survey reflects a win for Russian disinformation campaigns. Russian malign influence has successfully created an environment where nearly 39 percent of American adults surveyed believe something that is not aligned with reality.

How did we arrive at this juncture? This article will explore the timeline of Russia's invasion of Ukraine, some of the more egregious false narratives disseminated by Russia's disinformation campaign against Ukraine to date, the accurate information, and the primary sources of Russian disinformation.

¹ <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/02/19/world/europe/trump-zelenskyy-ukraine-comments.html>
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<https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/politics/2025/02/19/zelenskyy-hits-back-at-trump/79176501007/>

³ <https://today.yougov.com/topics/politics/survey-results/daily/2025/02/20/05ee7/4>
⁴

<https://today.yougov.com/topics/politics/survey-results/daily/2025/02/20/05ee7/4>

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A Brief History – The Warsaw Pact and NATO

In 1955, the Soviet Union formed a military alliance with Eastern European countries during the Cold War, known as the Warsaw Pact. This was in response to the West's NATO alliance. Ukraine was still part of Russia and didn't gain independence until August 24, 1991. However, there was a military-economic alliance between Poland and Ukraine in 1920 called the Treaty of Warsaw. Two years later, in 1922, Ukraine would be absorbed into the Soviet Union. That said, the original members of the Warsaw Pact were the Soviet Union, Albania, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, East Germany, Hungary, Poland, and Romania. The Soviet Union controlled most of the pact's decisions and directly reflected the USSR's authoritarianism and undisputed domination over the Eastern Bloc. The strategy behind the formation of the Warsaw Pact was driven by the Soviets' desire to prevent Central and Eastern Europe from being used as a base for military operations by NATO and the United States. As a result, each time a new member state is accepted into NATO, Russia has repeatedly accused the West of attempting to erode Russia's borders. The Warsaw Pact was dissolved in July of 1991. Ukraine gained independence in August of 1991, and the Soviet Union fell five months later in December 1991.

In 1989, two years before these three significant events, Russia's leaders claimed there was a verbal agreement for a "non-expansion of NATO to Eastern Europe". Soviet President Mikhail Gorbachev, who participated in the 1990 negotiations, subsequently spoke out about the existence of a "guarantee of non-expansion of NATO to the east"⁵ inconsistently, confirming its existence in some interviews and refuting it in others. "Among

academic researchers, opinions on the existence or absence of a non-extension agreement also differ."⁶ On May 17, 1990, the NATO Secretary General Manfred Wörner stated, "the very fact that we are not ready to deploy NATO troops outside the territory of Germany gives the Soviet Union firm guarantees."⁷ Russian leadership and authorities refer to this statement as a guarantee of the non-expansion of NATO beyond Germany.

Re-writing History

This claim that there was a non-expansion of the NATO agreement is relevant because Russian President Vladimir Putin and his two most high-profile diplomats have stated that Russia's decision to invade Ukraine was instigated by hostile encroachment by NATO expansions. Andrei Kelin, Putin's Ambassador to the United Kingdom, and Sergey Lavrov, Russia's Minister of Foreign Affairs, have recently praised President Trump for publicly aligning with Moscow's narrative that Ukraine started the war. In her BBC Newsnight interview, Victoria Derbyshire discussed Trump's remarks with Russian Ambassador Kelin. Earlier that week, Kelin stated, "For the first time, we have noticed that they [the US] are not simply saying that this is Russian propaganda and disinformation. They have listened, and they hear what we're saying."⁸ Minister Lavrov also lauded President Trump, saying, "He is the first, and so far, in my opinion, the only Western leader who has publicly and loudly said that one of the root causes of the Ukrainian situation was the impudent line of the previous administration to draw Ukraine into NATO."⁹

The official position of both Russian diplomats is that the previous U.S. support of Ukraine's bid to join the NATO military alliance was

⁵ Blomfield, Adrian; Smith, Mike (6 May 2008). "Gorbachev: US could start new Cold War". *The Daily Telegraph*.

⁶ Itzkowitz Shifrinson, Joshua R. (Spring 2016). "Deal or No Deal? The End of the Cold War and the U.S. Offer to Limit NATO Expansion". *International Security*. **40** (4). Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs. doi:10.1162/ISEC_a_00236. Archived from the original on 27 January 2024.

⁷ NATO Speech: The Atlantic Alliance and European Security". *Nato.int*. Retrieved 2 July 2022.

⁸ <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c36wn949jxno>

⁹ <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/russia-praises-trump-saying-nato-was-major-cause-war-ukraine-2025-02-19/>

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a significant cause of the war in Ukraine. Russia occupied and annexed Crimea in 2014. In August of that same year, Russia's military invaded the eastern Ukraine to support its separatist proxies (See figure 2.0 below). Even then, the Ukrainian people had no official request or outcry to join NATO. "In September 2022, Ukraine applied for NATO membership after Russia proclaimed it had annexed the country's southeast."¹⁰ Additionally, the Ukrainian public didn't show overwhelming support for joining NATO until the 2022 invasion.

Figure 2.0: "Assessed Control of Terrain in Ukraine and Main Russia Maneuver Axes" as of March 19, 2024 at 1500 EST. Map from Institute for the Study of War and CriticalThreats.¹¹

Russia's decision to invade Ukraine for the second time in eight years at the behest of President Vladimir Putin was one of the most significant motivators for non-member European states to apply

to NATO. Finland joined NATO in April 2023, followed by Sweden, the newest and 32nd member as of March 7, 2024. Finland shares an 833-mile border with Russia. It is important to remember that in February 2022, a Russian Foreign Ministry spokesperson threatened Finland and Sweden with military and political consequences if they attempted to join NATO. They both joined anyway and, in all probability, because of that threat. "Finnish President Saul Niinistö said Finland's most significant contribution to NATO's common deterrence and defense would be to defend its territory."¹² Russian aggression seems to be what makes NATO popular. This is not the first time Russia tried to justify its motivations to invade Ukraine with reasons that are less than truthful.

False Flag

Russia has attempted to frame Ukraine as the aggressor from the start. In January of 2022, CNN reported the following:

"The US has information that indicates Russia has prepositioned a group of operatives to conduct a false-flag operation in eastern Ukraine, a US official told CNN on Friday, in an attempt to create a pretext for an invasion. The official said the US has evidence that the operatives are trained in urban warfare and in using explosives to carry out acts of sabotage against Russia's proxy forces. Pentagon Press Secretary John Kirby said the Defense Department has credible information indicating Russia has pre-positioned a group of operatives to execute an operation designed to look like an attack on them or Russian-speaking people in Ukraine to create a reason for a potential invasion."¹³

The US intelligence community uncovered this information about Russia laying the groundwork of a fabricated pretext for an invasion. This is a job

¹⁰ "Ukraine applies for Nato membership after Russia annexes territory". *The Guardian*. 30 September 2022. Archived from the original on 1 October 2022. Retrieved 30 September 2022.

¹¹ <https://www.criticalthreats.org/analysis/russian-offensive-campaign-assessment-march-19-2024>

¹² <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/finland-set-join-nato-historic-shift-while-sweden-waits-2023-04-04/>

¹³ [First on CNN: US intelligence indicates Russia preparing operation to justify invasion of Ukraine | CNN Politics](https://www.cnn.com/2024/01/15/politics/russia-preparing-operation-ukraine/index.html)

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well done by US Intelligence. However, what was equally impressive was the US government's response. When the Biden administration released this information to the American and European public before Russia could execute the plan, it undermined Russia's malign influence operation and destroyed its false narrative. If the Biden administration White House had not preemptively disabled Russia's disinformation campaign, they could have potentially convinced the West their invasion was justified. This is why the executive branch cannot parrot the talking points of the Kremlin.

Tucker Carlson says, "Ukrainian churches are being burned and priests beaten."

In an April 2024 Tucker Carlson interview with lawyer Robert Amsterdam titled "Ukrainian churches are being burned and priest beaten,"¹⁴ a YouTube short with a clip included playing in the background of Tucker's interview suggest that a Ukrainian church was set ablaze allegedly by Ukraine's pro-western leadership, and/or its supporters. The disinformation tactic was effective. The false narrative quickly gained traction with the MAGA movement, who mostly opposed sending aid to Ukraine under their battle cry of "America First."

The video was a hoax and was proven to be disinformation almost immediately. The church burning in the video was a Ukrainian Greek Catholic church that caught fire in Canada in 2014. Another church on fire in the short clip was St. George's Church in the Kyiv Oblast town of Zavorychi. It was reportedly destroyed in a Russian strike in March 2022. "A third church on fire in the video is the Sviatohirsk Lavra in Donetsk Oblast, which was repeatedly struck by Russian artillery in May and June of 2022."¹⁵ The photo of the Sviatohirsk Lavra used in Carlson's video was a screenshot from a

video shared by Ukraine President Volodymyr Zelensky condemning the Russian attack, which he said killed four people and injured four others. To date, Tucker Carlson has not retracted his segment, nor has he accepted any responsibility for helping to shape the persistent and false claims that Ukraine is persecuting Christians. Robert Amsterdam, the lawyer Carlson was interviewing while showing false videos of burning churches, represents the Kremlin-linked Ukrainian Orthodox Church of the Moscow Patriarchate. Ukraine has two main Orthodox churches – the Ukrainian Orthodox Church of the Moscow Patriarchate, or UOC-MP, and the independent Orthodox Church of Ukraine (OCU). Some Orthodox Christians in Ukraine don't differentiate between the two.

The narrative of the persecution of Christians picked up steam after the "Ukraine parliament backed a bill in October 2023 to prohibit the activities of any religious organizations affiliated with war propaganda or justifying the Russian invasion of Ukraine. What followed was a series of accusations linking the UOC-MP to subversive actions guided by Russian intelligence."¹⁶ In comments to the Kyiv Independent, Amsterdam acknowledged the errors in Carlson's video but said he did not participate in its creation. He also added that the characterization of churches being burned in the video was "not completely accurate." Suppose there is any persecution of Christians in Ukraine. In that case, it is localized to the regions that Russia claimed after they annexed Ukraine's Crimea in 2014 and the subsequent covert invasion of parts of eastern Ukraine.

Despite having been thoroughly debunked, the "Ukraine persecuting Christians" narrative is a lie that many on the far right simply won't let die. Republican Rep. Marjorie Taylor Greene said in an interview last year, 2024, that Russia is "protecting

¹⁴ <https://kyivindependent.com/ukraine-fights-disinformation-not-christians-amid-russian-aggression/>

¹⁵ <https://kyivindependent.com/ukraine-fights-disinformation-not-christians-amid-russian-aggression/>

¹⁶ IBID

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Christianity"¹⁷ more than Ukraine, as part of what she described as a broader war against the religion. Greene, the two-term GOP lawmaker from Georgia, has been one of the more outspoken members of her party's conference over not providing continuous domestic aid to Ukraine in its two-plus year conflict with Russia since it was invaded on February 24, 2022. Rep. Green's remarks were made on the Real America's Voice - War Room segment, a right-wing to far-right streaming, cable, and satellite television channel founded in 2020. Some of the network's top personalities and influencers include Steve Bannon, Charlie Kirk, Ted Nugent, Gina Loudon, and John Solomon. Rep. Green's interview cycled through various other right-wing media outlets and was shared thousands of times on social media sites like Facebook and X (formerly Twitter).

Dictator without Elections

President Trump escalated his attacks against Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky on Wednesday, February 19, by calling him a "dictator without elections."¹⁸ Trump repeated the narrative on a Truth social post, stating: "Zelensky better move fast, or he is not going to have a Country left. I love Ukraine, but Zelensky has done a terrible job; his Country is shattered."¹⁹ Trump's statements were filtered through the usual conservative media outlets and far-right social media pages and reiterated by pro-MAGA influencers and supporters on nearly every platform.

The truth is that Zelensky was democratically elected in a fair and free election in 2019. Ukraine elections are held every five years. In May 2024, the Ukrainian parliament overwhelmingly voted to postpone the scheduled election in wartime due to the Russian invasion. This decision is also supported by

Ukraine's constitution. Ironically, President Trump has never called Russian President Putin a dictator.

The Hate Engines

In March of 2024, the New York Times reported that a "handful" of websites had appeared recently with names suggesting a focus on news close to home. For example: D.C. Weekly, the New York News Daily, the Chicago Chronicle and the Miami Chronicle. These sites are not domestic U.S.-based news organizations at all. They are the creations of a former Florida Sheriff named John Mark Dougan. Mark Dougan, according to the FBI records, was recruited by Russian intelligence services and now lives in Russia. Most of the sites have been shut down, only to have been restarted under new names. A few of the sites mentioned are managed here in the U.S. by Russian operatives; others are run in Russia. These sites aim to spread disinformation through stories about crime, politics, and culture.

The Foundation for Defense of Democracies published a Flash Brief on their webpage FDD.org on January 2, 2025, titled: "Sought to Divide the American People: U.S. Sanctions Iranian and Russian Entities Pushing Disinformation."²⁰ The article states that a Moscow-based group created a massive network of fake websites, contradicting the 2024 New York Times article that declared only a handful of bogus sites. As a result of these findings by the U.S. Department of Justice, "the U.S. Treasury Department sanctioned the Moscow-based Center for Geopolitical Expertise (CGE) and its director, Valery Mikhaylovich Korovin for its affiliation with Russia's military intelligence agency, the GRU. CGE personnel work directly with a GRU unit to conduct political interference operations and cyber warfare targeting the West. "The group used Generative AI to quickly create and disseminate disinformation about

¹⁷ <https://www.newsweek.com/marjorie-taylor-greene-applauds-russia-protecting-christianity-1888145>

¹⁸ <https://www.axios.com/2025/02/19/trump-zelensky-dictator-ukraine-russia-war>

¹⁹ IBID

²⁰ <https://www.fdd.org/analysis/2025/01/02/sought-to-divide-the-american-people-u-s-sanctions-iranian-and-russian-entities-pushing-disinformation/>

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U.S. candidates and other hot-button issues through a massive network of websites designed to imitate legitimate news outlets in the lead-up to the 2024 election.”²¹ Creating fake websites and using AI is now the primary strategy for pushing disinformation across media platforms worldwide.

The Russian fake websites operate like your typical online newspaper sites with Franklin Gothic and Times New Roman fonts. The deception works because many Americans presume the sites are authentic due to the mimicry of U.S.-based online news services. The similarity of appearance and formatting can give these fake sites the appearance of legitimacy. Readers who are deceived by these sites consume disinformation through fake news stories. One such phony news website, the Miami Chronicle, first appeared on Feb 26, 2024. Its tagline falsely claims to have delivered the “Florida News since 1937.” Another example is the Chicago Chronicle. The Chicago Chronicle was a legitimate newspaper from 1895 to 1907 before folding due to a lack of profitability. The online version is purely a creation of Russian Intelligence Services. “While Russia has long sought ways to influence public discourse in the United States, the fake news organizations — at least five, so far — represent a technological leap in its efforts to find new platforms to dupe unsuspecting American readers. The researchers and officials said the sites could well be the foundations of an online network primed to surface disinformation ahead of the American presidential election in November.”²²

One of the tactics that fictitious news outlets and Russian state-controlled news sites like Russia Today (RT News) and Radio Sputnik utilize to make themselves seem more authentic is to update regularly with real, significant breaking news. At

first glance, this practice creates the impression of relevance and legitimacy. For example, an article about the Supreme Court’s ruling about Mr. Trump’s eligibility to remain on the primary ballot in Colorado appeared on the Miami Chronicle’s site within hours of the decision. The websites tend to be poorly constructed, even incomplete in parts. The “about” page for the Miami Chronicle is filled with Latin-based dummy text. Some of the images on the site have file names from the original Russian. None of the sites post working contact information. “The purpose is not to fool a discerning reader into diving deeper into the website, let alone subscribing, Mr. Linvill said. The goal instead is to lend an aura of credibility to posts on social media spreading the disinformation.”²³ In other words, once readers strike confirmation bias pay dirt, they often cease the verification process.

Reliable Recent News (RRN), formerly Reliable Russian News, is one of the most egregious organizations in the Russian state news business. “Created in the aftermath of Russia’s invasion of the Ukraine, RRN, part of a bigger information-laundering operation known to investigators as Doppelganger, is primarily a ‘typosquatter’: a company that registers domain names that look similar to real media domain names- Reuters.cfd instead of Reuters.com, for example-as well as websites with names that sound authentic (like Notre Pays, or “Our Country”) but are created to deceive.”²⁴ During RRN’s short existence, it created more than 300 sites targeting Europe, the Middle East, and Latin America. Links to these sites are then used to make Facebook, Twitter, and other social media posts appear credible. When someone is quickly scrolling, they might not notice that a headline links to a fake Rueters.cfd website. Doppelganger, run by a clutch of companies in

²¹ IBID

²² Steven Lee Myers, *Spate of Mock News Sites with Russian Ties Pop Up in U.S.* March 7, 2024 [Spate of Mock News Sites With Russian Ties Pop Up in U.S. - The New York Times \(nytimes.com\)](https://www.nytimes.com/2024/03/07/us/politics/russia-fake-news-sites.html)

²³ Steven Lee Myers, *Spate of Mock News Sites with Russian Ties Pop Up in U.S.* March 7, 2024 [Spate of Mock News Sites With Russian Ties Pop Up in U.S. - The New York Times \(nytimes.com\)](https://www.nytimes.com/2024/03/07/us/politics/russia-fake-news-sites.html)

²⁴ [Anne Applebaum, “The New Propaganda War” The Atlantic June 2024 Issue](https://www.theatlantic.com/ideas/archive/2024/06/the-new-propaganda-war/674444/)

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Russia, systematically targets NATO by putting out fake press releases. These press releases are designed to seem authentic and “reveal” that NATO leaders are plotting various offensive operations and aggressive plans against Russia. The truth is that these press releases are fake, and the NATO plans are also fake. Yet, the damage is done because social media sites and legitimate news sites run with the phony narrative before the disinformation can be debunked.

D.C. Weekly is now shut down after claiming Ukraine President Volodymyr Zelenskyy’s wife purchased \$1.1 million worth of jewelry at the Cartier store in New York City during their visit to the United States in Sept 2023. Russian propaganda sites like D.C. Weekly and The New York News Daily are distribution networks primed to influence the American presidential elections. Patrick Warren, a co-director at Clemson University’s Media Forensics Hub, which has exposed furtive Russian disinformation efforts, said advances in artificial intelligence and other digital tools have “made this even easier to do and to make the content that they do even more targeted.”²⁵

According to the Office of the Director of National Intelligence (ODNI), RT and Sputnik are prominent Russian state-run outlets that target global audiences. They are not fake news sites in the same vein as D.C. Weekly or the Chicago Chronicle, which impersonated U.S.-based news outlets. RT (previously known as Russia Today) and Sputnik are Russian State-sponsored media, headquartered in Russia, but with regional editorial offices worldwide. Therefore, I contend that they still belong to fictitious news sites. The ODNI reports that the Russian government co-opts both RT and Sputnik to spread content that looks favorably upon Russia and fuels discontent in the United States. TR’s motto is

“Question more,” and Sputnik’s motto is “Telling the untold.” However, the mission for both isn’t to seek the truth. With only a casual look at their show descriptions, anyone can see that most shows are dedicated to exposing corruption and lies that they claim the mainstream media won’t tell you about. Of course, this is a false narrative. RT and Sputnik’s fundamental mission is to twist and weaponize information to fit the Russian propaganda ecosystem. “Since 2008, the network has invested in re-branding efforts that appeal more to Western audiences: changing its name from Russia Today to RT. During this time, RT also drastically changed its reporting focus from talking positively about Russian issues to persistently talking about the corruption in both the United States and Ukraine. “Sputnik seems to follow a very similar reporting model.”²⁶

Conclusion

Russia maintains its true advantage over the West in the information warfare space. To change this advantage in favor of democratic Western society, we must understand the information warfare ecosystem. To begin with, the Russian state-controlled media uses disinformation as its primary weapon. Simultaneously, a myriad of US media outlets spread disinformation domestically. The messages spread by Russian state media and certain domestic US media outlets are frequently aligned. Further investigation is required to determine if this is due to collusion, influence, or simply coincidence. However, the disinformation permeating American society is being represented as truth.

Both U.S.-based and foreign media outlets, as well as all social media platforms, serve as distribution networks for disinformation. Distribution networks that are proliferating disinformation to American audiences. The content

²⁵ Steven Lee Myers, *Spate of Mock News Sites with Russian Ties Pop Up in U.S.* March 7, 2024 [Spate of Mock News Sites With Russian Ties Pop Up in U.S. - The New York Times \(nytimes.com\)](https://www.nytimes.com/2024/03/07/us/politics/russia-ties-pop-up-in-u-s.html)

²⁶ Suzanne Spaulding, Devi Nair and Arthur Nelson, “*How the Kremlin Works to Undermine the U.S. Justice System*” Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) (2019) <http://www.jstor.com/stable/resrep22556.6>

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on these platforms is considered entertainment, not news. However, audiences extract a great deal of their information and form their beliefs via social media content. According to Pew Research's September 17, 2024, News Platform Factsheet, podcasts are where nearly 30 percent of US adults get their news. Podcasts have become very impactful in information warfare due to their massive popularity. In large part, this is due to ease of accessibility. The Pew Factsheet survey results indicate that most Americans get their news from a digital device. "A large majority of U.S. adult's 86 percent say they at least sometimes get news from a smartphone, computer or tablet, including 57 percent who say they do so often. These figures are almost identical to the share of people who got news from digital devices in 2023."²⁷ The fact sheet says that "there are several different pathways Americans use to get news on their digital devices. News websites or apps and search engines are the most common: About two-thirds of U.S. adults sometimes get news in each way. A little more than half 54 percent at least sometimes get news from social media, and 27 percent say the same about podcasts."²⁸

Finally, other media platforms deceptively present themselves as legitimate news source outlets

when they are fake news sites set up by U.S. citizens who are working with Russian intelligence services. While all the distribution methods of the information warfare ecosystem are important, the fake news sites are one of Russia's most brazen yet effective tactics. Therefore, while media literacy is crucial for Americans and has always been, it is now more critical than ever.

Too many Americans find themselves in a monsoon of information, struggling to decipher fact from fiction. For the U.S. to win the information warfare game in the future, we must have a relentless and well-defined strategy, especially for combating foreign malign influence. If we do not, Americans will likely accept the narrative from the loudest and most repetitive influencers in media. Influencers, whether knowing or unknowing agents of hostile states, have proven that they can persuade our entire nation that it is not in our best interest to support an allied nation. This is an anathema to our values, erodes trust with our allies, and strengthens our enemies. Therefore, the U.S. Government must be vigilant and proactive in its struggle to win the information warfare game.

Author Biography

Sean McKelvey is a Doctoral student at the Institute of World Politics with a focus on Russian foreign malign influence operations, and disinformation campaigns. In his career, Sean is a strategic communications/public affairs consultant with Science Applications International Corporation, (SAIC) supporting the Department of Defense. Specifically, Sean's SAIC contract title role is head of digital media supporting the Office of the Undersecretary of Defense for Research and Engineering, (OUSD R&E).

Photo by Markus Winkler: <https://www.pexels.com/photo/close-up-shot-of-a-typewriter-4160060/>

²⁷ [News Platform Fact Sheet, 2024 | Pew Research Center](#)

²⁸ [News Platform Fact Sheet, 2024 | Pew Research Center](#)

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